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15 Overview of the options in IC software 52

1 Author

This work instruction is written by Shanaya S. Soeknandan in favour of the NFI and the PyroProf Project and supervised by Carlos Martín Alberca. This document is written in the period of December 2018 till April 2019

2 Acknowledgment

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3 Specification instrument

- IC Methrom 850
- Auto sampler 919 Plus
 - o Capacity 56
- Waters Mass spectrometer Zspray ESI, Single Quadrupole
- UPLC pump
- Detector
- Pump A
- Pump B
- Suppressor
- Guard column
- Column methrom,
- Ventilation pump

4 Chemicals

- Oxalic Acid, from Sigma Alridch, 98% CAS 144-62-7
- Acetonitrile from Biosolve, ULC/MS-CC/SFC grade CAS 75-05-8
- Ultrapure water, (resistivity of 18.2 MΩ·cm at 21°C obtained from a Veolia Water ELGA system)
- Methanol from Biosolve, ULC/MS-CC/SFC grade CAS 67-56-1
- Isopropanol from Biosolve, LC-MS grade CAS 67-63-0
- Cations salts (multiple different suppliers)

4.1.1 Eluent for cation

The eluent for the cation method exists of 4,9mM OxAc + 25% Acetonitrile.

Because for some minor experiments less than 1Liter of eluent was necessary, two recipes are known.

Recipe for 2 Litre eluent:

OxAc: 0,8822 or 0,8823 grams (the 3rd decimal should be precise)

ACN: 500 ml

Ultrapure water: 1500 ml

Recipe for 1 Litre eluent:

OxAc: 0,4411 or 0,4412 grams (the 3rd decimal should be precise)

ACN: 250 ml

Ultrapure water: 750 ml

4.1.2 Eluent for cleaning the interphase

The eluent is composed out of 20% methanol and 80% Ultrapure water

4.1.3 Eluent for anion

For the anion part there are two eluent kinds. Eluent A is composed out of 34% acetonitrile in Ultrapure water with 5.0 mM sodium carbonate and 4.8 mM sodium bicarbonate. Eluent B exists out of 10% acetonitrile in Ultrapure water with 5.0 mM sodium carbonate and 4.8 mM sodium bicarbonate.

4.1.4 Eluent bottles

For the cation method there is only one eluent bottle containing 4,9mM Oxalic Acid + 25% Acetonitrile which is on top of the IC. Behind this bottle there are three bottles with Ultrapure water in it. These three bottles are for the suppressor and the second pump. There should always be Ultrapure water in those bottles when it is not being used. It keeps the wells in the IC system moist.

On top of the Waters MS there is another Eluent bottle containing 20% Methanol mixed with Ultrapure water. This eluent is used for the auto cleaning method. From time to time, depending on how often it is used, this eluent should be refilled.

4.1.5 Waste

There are 3 waste bottles. One is situated behind the IC and two are situated on the floor under the bench. The waste bottle in front to which two tubes are leading and the one behind the IC are the ones that are needed to be changed more often than the other one. In these waste bottles liquid waste containing hydrocarbon and halogens can be disposed. Even leftover eluent can be emptied in this waste bottle. All three waste bottles have the code UN3295. Each waste bottle should have a sticker of UN 3295 and a flammable sticker.

4.1.5.1 Photo of the instrument

MS cone

Eluent bottle

Interphase eluent

Bottles with Ultrapure water for the suppressor and pump

4.1.6 Standard Value's

Software	Standard value's
MassLynx (MS Tune) (method used for analysis)	Capillary Voltage: 1KV Desolvation temperature: 350 °C Desolvation gas: 1200L/Hr
MassLynx (MS Tune) (Shutdown method)	Desolvation gas:400L/Hr
IC (for analysis)	Running time: 26 min Flow: 1 ml/min Conductivity: approx. 665 uS/cm Pressure: 14,7 MPa Temperature: 30°C
IC (auto clean method)	Running time: 30 min Flow: 0,8 ml/min Pressure: 12,0 MPa
UPLC (flow used for auto/manual cleaning interphase)	Flow: 0,450 ml/min
MassLynx> Sample list> Bottle	Maximum number for this is 95
IC> Sample table	Maximum number of rows is 999
MassLynx (MS Tune)> Top left corner	Clean:...^6 or ...^7 Dirty: ...^8 or ...^9
IC> Sample information	Injection: 1 Volume: 20 µl Dilution: 1 Sample amount: 1

4.1.7 Methods in use

During the validation several methods have been developed and are in use now. To get acquainted with the methods see below information given about each method and when to use. *Note: It is possible that in future the names of the method can be changed so the names given below are without prejudice.*

Software	Name given to the method	When to use	Specifications of the method
IC	Cations-Isocratic	Analysis	Duration 26 min Flow: 1 ml/min
	Cations-AUTO Clean Method	Automatically cleaning interphase	Duration 30 min Flow: 0,8 ml/min
MassLynx (MS File)	22 Cation SIR	Analysis	Duration 26
	Cations AUTO cleaning method interphase	Automatically cleaning interphase	Duration 30 min
	22 cation SIR+MS	Analysis. In this method 5 full scans are include.	Duration 26 min Flow: 1 ml/min
MassLynx (Inlet File)	Cation_SIR 23min	Analysis. Note the name says 23 min but in reality it has a running time of 26 min.	Duration 26
	Cations_AUTO cleaning method for interphase	Automatically cleaning interphase	Duration 30 min
MS Tune	Shutdown 2.ipr	This is the auto shutdown method which should be selected at the end of a sequence.	Capillary voltage:1KV Desolvation temperature: 50°C Desolvation gas: 400L/Hr

5 General Information

In this chapter several important parts will be described. See below general information given about all the different options within each software.

5.1 IC software

See information protocol “ Ionchromatograaf Applikon juni 2016”

Information about the column can be found in the configuration tab in the IC software.

5.2 Describing the MassLynx software

The picture above is taken from the MassLynx program. This picture is divided in the six following parts, 1 Main menu, 2 Shortcut menu, 3 Sample information bar, 4 Status of the MS & 5 Shutdown, 6 System status.

1 Main menu: has 11 icons. From left to right: open a file, creating a new file/ sample list, Loading a sample list, Save, Print, Play, Stop, Pause, Shortcut, Queue, Status.

2 Shortcut menu: For access to this shortcut menu, click on the shortcut icon in the main menu. This menu exists of four independent tabs. From top to bottom: Instrument, Tools, Openlynx & TargetLynx. See chapter 5.4 Shortcut menu

3 Sample information bar: In this area of the MassLynx there are several important buttons. Spectrum, Chromatogram, Map, Edit, Samples, File name, Sample ID, File text, Ms File, Ms Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc A, Sample Group. In this Sample information menu more categories can be added to. See chapter Sample information bar.

4 Status of the MS: Show the status of the MS. When the instrument is not analysing it shows “Not Scanning”. When a row has been selected and play button has already been hit then at first it shows “Acquiring”. After a few seconds then the status is “Waiting for inlet 1”. Acquiring means that an analysis is going on. Waiting for inlet 1 means that the instrument is waiting for the start signal given by the IC.

5 Shutdown: If clicked on this icon/button a screen pops up with few options. For example in this screen you can un-/checkmark the auto shutdown method. After doing that always save the settings. It does not automatically save the settings after an adjustment. See chapter 5.6 shutdown.

6 System status: Shows the current status of the system.

5.3 Main menu

Out of the eleven icons a few are highlighted. Play, Shortcut, Queue & status.

5.3.1 Main menu: Play

This is the play button. By clicking on the play button the selected rows will be submitted to the queue. *Note: always fill in the list first in both software's then start the MS first then start the IC.*

5.3.2 Main menu : Shortcut

By clicking on this icon you can access the sub tabs in the shortcut menu (more information in chapter 5.4).

5.3.3 Main menu: Queue

View all analysis pending and the current analysis being analysed.

1. Click in the "Main menu" on "Queue"
2. Screen pops up. In this screen you can see the details of the selected analysis added to the sequence. It is possible to delete the selected analysis. For that click on delete process. Make sure you delete the same rows in the IC list as well.

5.3.4 Main menu: Status

View the current status of the MS and LC in one blink. If everything is working proper then a green light is visible, if something is wrong a red light appears (photo left: working proper, photo right: not working proper). On the left side there are shortcut buttons for several software's. These shortcuts will be explained in an upcoming chapter.

5.4 Shortcut menu

As mentioned before the shortcut menu can be divided into several tabs.

5.4.1 Shortcut menu: Instrument

You can access this tab by clicking on “shortcut icon” in the main menu, then click on “instrument”.

The screenshot displays the Masslynx software interface. On the left side, a vertical toolbar contains several icons. The 'Instrument' icon, which depicts a laboratory instrument, is circled in red. The main window area shows a table with columns for 'File Name', 'Sample ID', 'File Text', 'MS File', 'MS Tune File', 'Inlet File', 'Bottle', 'Inject Volume', 'Sample Type', 'Conc. A', and 'Quan Reference'. The table lists various sample files and their corresponding parameters. At the bottom of the interface, the system status is shown as 'Ready'.

File Name	Sample ID	File Text	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Bottle	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc. A	Quan Reference
1768 20180312_NVEE_1ed,911an1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	23	0.000			
1770 20180313_NVEE_1ed,2R1-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	24	0.000			
1771 20180313_NVEE_1ed,7R1-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	25	0.000			
1772 20180313_1st 2pm-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	26	0.000			
1773 20180313_MIQ 2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	27	0.000			
1774 20180313_NVEE_1ed,8RS-3101		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	28	0.000			
1775 20180313_NVEE_1ed,2R3		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	29	0.000			
1776 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	30	0.000			
1777 20180313_NVEE_1ed,911an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	31	0.000			
1778 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	32	0.000			
1779 20180313_1st 2pm-3		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	33	0.000			
1780 20180313_MIQ 3		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	34	0.000			
1781 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	35	0.000			
1782 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	36	0.000			
1783 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	37	0.000			
1784 20180313_NVEE_1ed,911an1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	38	0.000			
1785 20180313_NVEE_1ed,911an-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	39	0.000			
1786 20180313_1st 2pm-4		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	40	0.000			
1787 20180313_MIQ 4		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	41	0.000			
1788 20180313_NVEE_1ed,9R1-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	42	0.000			
1789 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	43	0.000			
1790 20180313_NVEE_1ed,911an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	44	0.000			
1791 20180313_NVEE_1ed,231an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	45	0.000			
1792 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-3		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	46	0.000			
1793 20180313_1st 2pm-5		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	47	0.000			
1794 20180313_MIQ 5		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	48	0.000			
1795 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	49	0.000			
1796 20180313_NVEE_1ed,911an-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	50	0.000			
1797 20180313_NVEE_1ed,9R3-3		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	51	0.000			
1798 20180313_NVEE_1ed,9R2-2		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	52	0.000			
1799 20180313_NVEE_1ed,91an1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	53	0.000			
1800 20180313_NVEE_1ed,24mp-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	54	0.000			
1801 20180313_1st 2pm-6		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	55	0.000			
1802 20180313_MIQ 1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	1	0.000			
1803 20180313_1st 1pm-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	2	0.000			
1804 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment G-1		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	3	0.000			
1805 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment G-2		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	4	0.000			
1806 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment G-3		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	5	0.000			
1807 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment G-4		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	6	0.000			
1808 20180313_MIQ 2		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	7	0.000			
1809 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment H-1		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	8	0.000			
1810 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment H-2		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	9	0.000			
1811 20180313_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment H-3		18 Cation SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Cation_SIR 33min Robustness expG	10	0.000			
1812 20180320_MIQ		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	11	0.000			
1813 20180320_1pm-18c-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	12	0.000			
1814 20180320_MIQ		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	13	0.000			
1815 20180320_S1d 1pm-18cations Robustness experiment L-1		22 Cation SIR		Default	Cation_SIR_23am	14	0.000			

5.4.1.1 Shortcut menu: Instrument-Inlet Method

The inlet method corresponds the UPLC-pump. In here several commands can be given (see chapter 5.4.1.1.1. Subtab: modifying the UPLC method). The instrument will do as the commands say. The green lights means that it's working. So if there are greens lights for Ready and OK, then the instrument is ready for use. If there is a green light for running then the instrument is currently running, busy with a analysis. If there is a red light then there could be a problem with the communication. 1: the Inlet Method icon, 2: sub tab to modify the method, 3: pumping icon (which mean that it is/not pumping. If the icon is like in the picture below it means that is not pumping. If the icon changed and now a blue drop is also visible then that means that the UPLC is pumping.), 4: Loading a method (normally when a method is adjusted, it is advisable to click on this icon if the adjusted method is going to be used right away).

5.4.1.1.1 Sub tab: modifying the UPLC method

In this subtab it is possible to adjust or create a new inlet method according to the requirements. The parameters for the analysis are shown in the picture below, currently the running time is extended till 26 min instead of 23min.

If a new method requires different parameters, adjust the method as wished. The running time can be extended or shortened (note: if the running time is adjusted, then the running time should be adjusted in all 3 software's). The solvents can be adjusted depending on what is being used. The Flow can be adjusted. Commands such as start the flow at a certain time point, stop the flow at certain time point, change the flow from 1ml/min to 0,45 ml/min. For example open the inlet file with the name "Cations_AUTO cleaning method for interphase". Compare both parameters. There are some differences visible. Comparing different methods can be a guidance for trying new commands. After adding some changes or creating a new one save this method under a new name.

5.4.2 Shortcut menu: Tools

You can access this tab by clicking on “shortcut icon” in the main menu, then click on “tools”.

No information recovered yet

5.4.3 Shortcut menu: OpenLynx

You can access this tab by clicking on “shortcut icon” in the main menu, then click on “Openlynx”.

No information recovered yet

5.4.4 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx

You can access this tab by clicking on the “shortcut icon” in the main menu, then click on “TargetLynx”. TargetLynx can be divided in six tabs. Each tab can again be divided into more tabs.

The screenshot shows the TargetLynx software interface. The main menu on the left includes icons for Edit Method, Process Samples, View Results, TrendPlot, Quapedia, and QCMonitor Email. The 'Shortcut' icon is highlighted with a red circle. The main window displays a table with columns: File Name, Sample ID, File Test, MS File, MS Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Injct Volume, Sample Type, Conc A, and Quan Reference. The table contains 40 rows of data, including sample IDs like 1763, 1770, 1771, etc., and various file names and test results.

5.4.4.1 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-Edit Method

In Edit method a lot of information about the method is shown and can be modified. Also a reason not the keep this window opened without any reason because even by an accidental click on something this method can be modified.

In this software a lot of options are present such as quantification ion, noise range ect...

The screenshot shows the TargetLynx software interface with the 'Edit Method' window open. The 'Edit Method' icon in the main menu is highlighted with a red circle. The 'Edit Method' window displays a 'Compound List' on the left, listing various elements and compounds such as Urea, Ammonium, Sodium, Magnesium, Potassium, Strontium, Ethylammonium, Nickel, Cobalt, Aluminum, Copper, Lithium, Dicyandiamide, Barium, Calcium, Manganese, Iron II, Dureny Channel, Cadmium, Zinc, Cesium, Gadolinium, and Lead. The right side of the window shows 'Target Ion Properties' for each compound, including 'Use Quant Ion in Response Calculation?', 'Target Ion RT Window (mins) ±', 'Target Ion Ratio Method', 'Calculate Ion Ratio Tolerance As Ratio', 'Update Ion Ratios Using Multiple Samples?', 'View First Target Ion Parameters', 'View Second Target Ion Parameters', 'View Third Target Ion Parameters', and 'View Fourth Target Ion Parameters'. Each property has a corresponding value or checkbox.

5.4.4.2 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-Proces samples

See chapter 8: Processing data: TargetLynx

5.4.4.3 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-View Results

No information recovered yet

5.4.4.4 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-Trendplot

This software can be used for creating a trend plot of multiple analysis. For example: 20 days in a row a standard of 1ppm was analysed every day. While processing the data you can open all those 1 ppm standards in trendplot to view the process of the standard. Trendplot can give a graph like a calibration curve. *So far there is no maximum of analysis knows*

5.4.4.5 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-Quanpedia

No information recovered yet

5.4.4.6 Shortcut menu: TargetLynx-QCMonitor Email

No information recovered yet

5.5 Sample information bar

Sample information bar: In this area of the MassLynx there are several important options and categories. Spectrum, Chromatogram, Map, Edit, Samples, File name, Sample ID, File text, Ms File, Ms Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc A, Sample Group. In this Sample information bar more categories can be added to. See chapter Sample information bar.

5.6 Shutdown

Note: after a long sequences use the auto shutdown method. For the auto shutdown method do the following:

1. Click on the right bottom icon “shutdown disabled” (If the auto shutdown is already selected then is displays “Only batch shutdown enabled”).
2. Checkmark the second box and click on “save”.
3. The click on “close”. Also check mark the box in the IC software.

5.7 The UPLC-software

This software is related to the UPLC pump in the IC-MS system. Most often screen used in this software is the “interactive display”. In this display there is an overview of the whole UPLC-system.

5.8 The MS tune

There are several important parameters/icons and tabs. For more information view the waters manual.

Fig 1 MS Tune-ES+ tab

- 1: API gas: the gas that flows through the system.
- 2: Several tabs: ES+, Fluidics, Extended, Diagnostics.
- 3: Value
- 4: Expand: Press this icon to un-zoom.
- 5: Switch On/Off

Several tabs: Fluidics

In the tab “Fluidics” pay attention to the valve position. There are four positions. Waste, Interphase, combined and LC. The MS switches automatically to the LC because it’s implemented in the method for an analysis. When cleaning the interphase manually, change the valve to interphase (see chapter 6: How to clean the interphase).

Fig 2 MS Tune-Fluidics tab

Several tabs: Extended

No information recovered yet

Fig 3 MS Tune-Extended tab

Several tabs: Diagnostics

In here the status of each parameter is shows. If there any red squares, pay attention to that. Could be that the MS is still off, the MS door is not well closed or something else.

Fig 4 MS Tune-Diagnostics

6 How to clean the interface

In this software/ program it is possible to clean the interphase manually. Clean the interphase means, cleaning the MS with a different eluent (20% Methanol/Ultrapur water).

1. Go to the MS-console.
2. Change the “valve position” to infusion.
3. Go to the UPLC software
 - a. Click on the tab “control”
 - i. Click on “set flow” and change the flow from 0 to 0, 45 ml/min, click on “green checkmark”
 - ii. After clean for approx. 30 minutes, click on “control”, click on “stop flow”.
To check whether the MS is clean enough, go to the live display of the MS tune. If the value, top left corner is approx. ...⁶ or ...⁷, it can be considered as clean. If the value is still approx. ...⁸ or ...⁹ it is still dirty and need to be cleaned longer.

Fig 1 MS console

Fig 2 UPLC software

7 Creating a new method

If a new method need to be created pay attention to several thing. For adjusting a method, changes should be made in three software's (IC, MS file and Inlet file).

7.1 Adjusting the IC

Pay attention to the running time. Can be found in "Method", click on "CATION ", "data aquisition"
Change the running time.

The screenshot shows the MagIC Net 3.1 software interface. The 'Recording time' is set to 25 minutes. The 'Time program' table is as follows:

Time	Device	Module	Command	Parameter	Comment	No.
0.0	850 Professional IC 1	Injector An	Pin			1
0.0	919 IC Autosampler plus 1	Tower	Move (Back)	Sample position		30
0.0	919 IC Autosampler plus 1	Tower	Lift	Work position		8
0.0	919 IC Autosampler plus 1	Peristaltic	On/OFF	On, Rate=3		9
0.0	919 IC Autosampler plus 1	Peristaltic	Wait	Continue after 1 min.		3
0.0	919 IC Autosampler plus 1	Peristaltic	On/OFF			10
0.0	850 Professional IC 1	Injector An	Inject			4
0.0	Cations		Start data acquisition			2
0.0	mhb		Set lines	1111111111111111		7
0.0	mhb		Parallel	Cleaning		10
0.5	mhb		Set lines	00000000000000		11

The 'Chromatograms' window shows a chromatogram with peaks labeled at retention times 2.74, 4.25, 6.34, 12.4, and 29.7 minutes.

7.2 Adjusting the Inlet File

Change the running time and commands if necessary and save this method under a new.

The screenshot shows the 'Modify Instrument Method' dialog box in BSM software. The 'Run Time' is set to 23.00 minutes. The 'Solvents' section shows A1 as Methanol and B1 as Water. The 'Pressure Limits' are set to Low: 0 psi and High: 15000 psi. The 'Gradient' table is as follows:

	Time (min)	Flow (mL/min)	%A	%B	Curve
1	Initial	0.000	100.0	0.0	Initial
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					

The 'Seal Wash' is set to 5.0 minutes. The 'Gradient Start' is set to 'At injection'.

7.3 Adjusting the MS File: SIR method

SIR stands for single ion recording. This is the same method/file which is selected in the MS list-MS File. This method is all about the programming of each ion duration of the run, retention time window etc.

1. To access the SIR method click in MassLynx on “instrument” then “MS method” The screen below pops up.

2. Shorten/ extend the running time: The most simple way is to double click on the dummy channel. A new screen pops up (photo on the right). Change the end/start time as wish. Click on “OK” So can the retention time window for each ion in the list be adjusted. Repeat for those ions which need to be adjusted.

The screenshot shows the MassLynx interface with the SIR method configuration window open. The window has a table with the following data:

Compound Name	Mass (m/z)	Auto Dwell	Dwell (s)	Cone (V)
Dutality	111.0000	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0.053	10

The 'End' time in the 'Retention Window (Min)' section is set to 26 and is circled in red.

3. Click on “options” and then on “Method events”. A screen pops up (right photo). Adjust the running time to the exact time changed at step 2. Commands can be add/removed/changed.

1st row: Flow state waste (means after the start signal at min 0.10 the flow state will go to position waste)

2nd row: Flow state LC (means at min 1.00 the position switch from waste to LC so the run is starting)

3rd row: Flow state waste (means at min 25.80 the position switches from LC to waste. The analysis the almost done) This time point needs to be 0.2 min earlier than the end of running time.

The screenshot shows the 'Method events' configuration window. The table contains the following data:

Time / Mins	Event	Action
0.00	Flow State Waste	On
1.00	Flow State LC	Waste
25.80	Flow State Waste	Waste

The 'Initial Settings' section shows:

- Stop flow: No Change
- Switch 2: No Change
- Switch 3: No Change
- Switch 4: No Change
- Inclusion: No Change
- Flow State: LC
- Flow Rate µl/min: 200.0
- Reservoir: No Action
- Refill: No Action
- Volume µl: 250
- Solvent Delay Options:
 - API Probe Temperature °C: 20

8 Routine

8.1 How to change the eluent

1. Go to tab "equilibration". Press stop if the IC is still pumping eluent through the system/ in working mode. *Note: that before changing the eluent the flow should be 0 ml/min and pressure should be zero (at least below 1MPa).*
2. Change the eluent.
 - a. Unscrew the green part of the cap. Do not twist the tubing of the eluent bottle.
 - b. Change bottle. Make sure that the tube from the eluent is not in contact with the PEEK tube (natural colour). Also do not touch the tube from the eluent with bare hands/ gloves. Do not let the tip of the eluent tubing touch the top surface of the IC.
 - c. Screw the green part on the new bottle.
 - d. Put the bottle with old eluent back in the chemical cabinet or throw the eluent in the waste bottle UN 3295.
3. Go to the "method" icon on the left.
 - a. Go to the tab "pump A".
 - b. Change the flow rate to 0,8 ml/min.
 - c. Click on save
4. Go to the "workplace" icon
 - a. Click on the equilibration" tab
 - b. Press "start"
 - c. Let the instrument equilibrate for minimum 10 minutes. Check the live display window whether the baseline and pressure is stable. If so change the flow rate from 0,8 ml/min to 1,0 ml/min. If not, wait until the baseline and pressure is stable enough and then change it. After changing the flow to 1,0 ml/min, let the column equilibrate for another 15 min. In total it takes +/- 25 minutes to equilibrate the column. Depending on the eluent it could take longer to equilibrate. (Eluent 25% ACN + 4,9mM OxAc it takes 15 min to equilibrate at flow 0,8ml/min with a pressure of 12,0 MPa. Then it takes 10 min at flow 1ml/min for a stable pressure of 14,7 MPa)

8.2 How to clean the tubes in the autosampler

Meanwhile the equilibration it going on, clean the falcon tubes, injection needle and special beaker. If the injection needle is in the beaker, make sure the needle is in a different position. Go to "manual" icon, click on tab "tower", enter 0 or home position in "lift position" and press start (injector will go up). Then in order to reach the beaker, enter a random number in "rack-position" and press start (the rack will go to that position).

1. Items to clean: four falcon tubes, injector and special beaker.
 - a. The positions of the items:
 - i. Position 52: falcon tube 1 contains 80% Isopropanol: Ultrapure water
 - ii. Position 53: falcon tube 2 contains 50% Isopropanol: Ultrapure water
 - iii. Position 54: falcon tube 3 contains 20% Isopropanol: Ultrapure water

- iv. Position 55: falcon tube 4 contains Ultrapure water
- v. Position 56: falcon tube 5 contains Ultrapure water
- vi. Special beaker contains Ultrapure water
- b. Depending on the ratio between Ultrapure water and Isopropanol make that solution. Close the tubes with their caps and put them in the right position.
- c. Rinse (three times) the special beaker with Isopropanol and fill the beaker with Ultrapure water till 0.5cm from the upper edge. Place the beaker back.

8.3 Cleaning the MS-Cone

1. Switch off the API gas
2. Switch off the MS
3. Open the MS door (there is a grey handle on the right side, pull it with little bit of force)
4. Wear heat resistance gloves and put a tissue underneath the door so the liquid doesn't leak on the floor.
5. There is an arrow pointed horizontal, gentle place the arrow vertically.
6. Take out the little part looking like a spoon. And place it in a piece of glassware and add Ultrapure water. So it's cools down.
7. When standing right in front of the MS, with door open, there is a black hex/ allen key hidden in the MS (top right corner). Use this tool to separate the O-ring from the spoon so both parts can be cleaned evenly. Clean with Ultrapure water and with methanol when is has cooled down. Afterwards dry both part with nitrogen gas before reassembling the part in the MS.
8. Rinse the door from the inside with Ultrapure water, 3 times
9. Rinse the door from the inside either with ethanol or methanol. *Note: Methanol has a dangerous vapour when the liquid is in contact with the hot element of the MS.*
10. Place everything back and place the arrow horizontal before closing the MS door.

8.4 How to switch the MS on

1. Load the correct method: default.ipr check the standard value's.
Capillary voltage 1KV, Desolvation temperature 350 °C, Desolvation gas 1200L/Hr.
Note: The "default.ipr" method which is used for the analysis has a desolvation gas of 1200L/Hr. The "Shutdown 2.ipr" method has a desolvation gas of 400L/Hr.
2. Then click on the right bottom button to switch the MS on (when it's on it will be green, if red, it means switched off)

The screenshot displays the TargetLynx software interface. The main window is titled 'Queue Is Empty'. On the left, there is a sidebar with icons for 'TargetLynx', 'OpenLynx', 'Instrument', 'Tools', and 'QC Monitor Email'. The central area is divided into several sections:

- File Name List:** A list of files with names like '20181122_9', '20181122_10', etc., and their corresponding dates and times.
- Diagnosics Tab:** This tab is active and shows various parameters:
 - Source Voltages: 1.00 (1.00)
 - Capillary (kV): 45 (40)
 - Source Temperature: 343 (350)
 - Desolvation Temp (°C): 343 (350)
 - Source Gas Flow: 1133 (1200)
 - Desolvation (L/Hr): 1133 (1200)
 - Core (L/Hr): 50 (50)
 - LM Resolution: 15.0
 - HM Resolution: 15.0
 - Ion Energy: 0.5
- Mass Scan Table:** A table with columns 'Mass', 'Scan', and 'Gain'. It shows data points for mass values 150, 97, 58.08, and 62.
- Acquisition Status:** At the bottom, it says 'Acquisition complete' and 'Vacuum Ok'. There is a green indicator light next to the 'Up' button, which is circled in red in the image.

9 Starting an analysis

1. Prepare the sample in a 2 ml vial and place this in an available position in the rack. Note: write on the side of the vial a code or something that defines the sample.
2. Right click on the last line.
3. Click on add (a new line is added to the list)

The screenshot shows the Masslynx software interface with a list of samples. The 'Add' option in the context menu is highlighted in yellow. The table below represents the data visible in the software interface.

File Name	Sample ID	File Text	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Boilte	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc. A	Quan Reference
1241	201908_50	SWABMLSC	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	62	0.000			
1242	201908_51	SWABMLSC	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	63	0.000			
1243	201908_52	SWABML7C	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	64	0.000			
1244	201908_53	SWABMLSC	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	65	0.000			
1245	201908_54	SWABMLSC	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	66	0.000			
1246	201908_55	SWABML10C	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	67	0.000			
1247	201908_57	MIIQ auto clean		Default	CaIons_AUTO cleaning method interphase		0.000			
1248	20190213_01	MIIQ	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	1	0.000			
1249	20190213_02	1ppm 18 cal after cleaning ion guide	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	2	0.000			
1250	20190213_03	1ppm 18 cal after cleaning ion guide-2	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	3	0.000			
1251	20190213_04	1ppm 18 cal after cleaning ion guide-3	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	4	0.000			
1252	20190213_05	1ppm 18 cal after cleaning ion guide-4	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	5	0.000			
1253	20190214_01	MIIQ	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	6	0.000			
1254	20190214_02	1ppm 18 cal after calibration-1	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	7	0.000			
1255	20190214_03	1ppm 18 cal after calibration-2	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	8	0.000			
1256	20190214_04	1ppm 18 cal after calibration-3	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	9	0.000			
1257	20190214_05	MIIQ	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	10	0.000			
1258	20190214_06	10ppb Calcium standard-1	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	11	0.000			
1258	20190214_07	10ppb Calcium standard-2	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	12	0.000			
1260	20190214_08	50ppb Calcium standard-1	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	13	0.000			
1261	20190214_09	50ppb Calcium standard-2	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	14	0.000			
1262	20190214_10	MIIQ auto clean		Default	CaIons_AUTO cleaning method interphase		0.000			
1263	20190215_01	MIIQ	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	16	0.000			
1264	20190215_02	1ppm 18 cal	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	17	0.000			
1265	20190215_03	1ppm 18 cal-2	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	18	0.000			
1266	20190215_04	MIIQ	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	19	0.000			
1267	20190215_05	Table blank	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	20	0.000			
1268	20190215_06	SWABML1D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	21	0.000			
1268	20190215_07	SWABML2D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	22	0.000			
1270	20190215_08	SWABML3D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	23	0.000			
1271	20190215_09	SWABML4D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	24	0.000			
1272	20190215_10	SWABML5D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	25	0.000			
1273	20190215_11	SWABML6D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	26	0.000			
1274	20190215_12	SWABML7D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	27	0.000			
1275	20190215_13	SWABML8D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	28	0.000			
1276	20190215_14	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	29	0.000			
1277	20190215_15	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	30	0.000			
1278	20190215_16	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	31	0.000			
1279	20190215_17	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	32	0.000			
1280	20190215_18	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	33	0.000			
1281	20190215_19	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	34	0.000			
1282	20190215_20	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	35	0.000			
1283	20190215_21	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	36	0.000			
1284	20190215_22	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	37	0.000			
1285	20190215_23	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	38	0.000			
1286	20190215_24	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	39	0.000			
1287	20190215_25	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	40	0.000			
1288	20190215_26	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	41	0.000			
1289	20190215_27	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	42	0.000			
1290	20190215_28	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	43	0.000			
1291	20190215_29	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	44	0.000			
1292	20190215_30	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	45	0.000			
1293	20190215_31	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	46	0.000			
1294	20190215_32	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	47	0.000			
1295	20190215_33	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	48	0.000			
1296	20190215_34	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	49	0.000			
1297	20190215_35	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	50	0.000			
1298	20190215_36	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	51	0.000			
1299	20190215_37	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	52	0.000			
1300	20190215_38	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	53	0.000			
1301	20190215_39	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	54	0.000			
1302	20190215_40	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	55	0.000			
1303	20190215_41	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	56	0.000			
1304	20190215_42	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	57	0.000			
1305	20190215_43	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	58	0.000			
1306	20190215_44	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	59	0.000			
1307	20190215_45	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	60	0.000			
1308	20190215_46	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	61	0.000			
1309	20190215_47	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	62	0.000			
1310	20190215_48	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	63	0.000			
1311	20190215_49	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	64	0.000			
1312	20190215_50	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	65	0.000			
1313	20190215_51	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	66	0.000			
1314	20190215_52	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	67	0.000			
1315	20190215_53	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	68	0.000			
1316	20190215_54	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	69	0.000			
1317	20190215_55	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	70	0.000			
1318	20190215_56	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	71	0.000			
1319	20190215_57	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	72	0.000			
1320	20190215_58	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	73	0.000			
1321	20190215_59	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	74	0.000			
1322	20190215_60	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	75	0.000			
1323	20190215_61	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	76	0.000			
1324	20190215_62	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	77	0.000			
1325	20190215_63	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	78	0.000			
1326	20190215_64	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	79	0.000			
1327	20190215_65	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	80	0.000			
1328	20190215_66	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	81	0.000			
1329	20190215_67	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	82	0.000			
1330	20190215_68	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	83	0.000			
1331	20190215_69	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	84	0.000			
1332	20190215_70	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	85	0.000			
1333	20190215_71	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	86	0.000			
1334	20190215_72	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	87	0.000			
1335	20190215_73	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	88	0.000			
1336	20190215_74	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	89	0.000			
1337	20190215_75	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	90	0.000			
1338	20190215_76	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	91	0.000			
1339	20190215_77	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	92	0.000			
1340	20190215_78	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	93	0.000			
1341	20190215_79	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	94	0.000			
1342	20190215_80	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	95	0.000			
1343	20190215_81	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	96	0.000			
1344	20190215_82	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	97	0.000			
1345	20190215_83	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	98	0.000			
1346	20190215_84	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	99	0.000			
1347	20190215_85	SWABML9D	22	Default	CaIons_SIR ...	100	0.000			

- Optional: change the date if necessary. Note: If it's the first analysis of the day always start with the date_01. Always use a "zero" for the first analysis if date is changed. If the writing style like 20190319_1 is used then it can create problem in future when analysis are sorted by group. After sorting based on group and then switched back to the normal setting, then some analysis can appear random somewhere in the list because it's sorts based on the number. For example if the notation of 20190319_1 is used (there are 30 samples starting from...._1 till...._30) then it will appear 20190319_1 will appear not before 20190319_2 but before 20190319_10.

Masslynx - PyroProf_Project - Pyroprof_CationMethod_Carlos.SPL

File View Run Help

Queue Is Empty

Instrument: Spectrum Chromatogram Map Edit Samples

File Name	Sample ID	File Text	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Bottle	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc A	Quan Reference
1241 201908_50	SWABML5C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	62	0.000			
1242 201908_51	SWABML5C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	63	0.000			
1243 201908_52	SWABML5C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	64	0.000			
1244 201908_53	SWABML5C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	65	0.000			
1245 201908_54	SWABML5C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	66	0.000			
1246 201908_55	SWABML10C		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	67	0.000			
1247 201908_57	MIQI auto clean	caton AUTO cleaning method interphase		Default	Cations_AUT ...	69	0.000			
1248 20190213_01	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	1	0.000			
1249 20190213_02	1ppm 18 cat after cleaning ion guide		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	2	0.000			
1250 20190213_03	1ppm 18 cat after cleaning ion guide-2		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	3	0.000			
1251 20190213_04	1ppm 18 cat after cleaning ion guide-3		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	4	0.000			
1252 20190213_05	1ppm 18 cat after cleaning ion guide-4		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	5	0.000			
1253 20190214_01	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	6	0.000			
1254 20190214_02	1ppm 18 cat after calibration-1		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	7	0.000			
1255 20190214_03	1ppm 18 cat after calibration-2		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	8	0.000			
1256 20190214_04	1ppm 18 cat after calibration-3		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	9	0.000			
1257 20190214_05	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	10	0.000			
1258 20190214_06	10ppb Calcium standard1		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	11	0.000			
1259 20190214_07	10ppb Calcium standard2		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	12	0.000			
1260 20190214_08	50ppb Calcium standard1		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	13	0.000			
1261 20190214_09	50ppb Calcium standard2		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	14	0.000			
1262 20190214_10	MIQI auto clean	caton AUTO cleaning method interphase		Default	Cations_SIR ...	15	0.000			
1263 20190215_01	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	16	0.000			
1264 20190215_02	1ppm 18 cat		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	17	0.000			
1265 20190215_03	1ppm 18 cat-2		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	18	0.000			
1266 20190215_04	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	19	0.000			
1267 20190215_05	Table blank		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	20	0.000			
1268 20190215_06	SWABML1D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	21	0.000			
1269 20190215_07	SWABML2D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	22	0.000			
1270 20190215_08	SWABML3D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	23	0.000			
1271 20190215_09	SWABML4D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	24	0.000			
1272 20190215_10	SWABML5D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	25	0.000			
1273 20190215_11	SWABML6D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	26	0.000			
1274 20190215_12	SWABML7D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	27	0.000			
1275 20190215_13	SWABML8D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	28	0.000			
1276 20190215_14	SWABML9D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	29	0.000			
1277 20190215_15	SWABML10D		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	30	0.000			
1278 20190215_16	MIQI		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	31	0.000			
1279 20190215_17	1ppm 18cat		22 Cation SIR	Default	Cations_SIR ...	32	0.000			
1280 20190215_18	7cations-extracted-Cr,Sr,Mn,K,Na,Al,Cu		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	33	0.000			
1281 20190215_19	7cations non-extracted-Cr,Sr,Mn,K,Na,Al,Cu		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	34	0.000			
1282 20190215_20	7cations-extracted-lower-conc-Cr,Sr,Mn,K,Na,Al,Cu		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	35	0.000			
1283 20190219_06	Robustness-exp A - 1ppm 18cat-1		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	6	0.000			
1284 20190219_07	Robustness-exp A-1 - 1ppm 18cat-2		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	6	0.000			
1285 20190219_08	Robustness-exp A-1 - 1ppm 18cat-3		16 Cation SIR 15min	Default	Cations_SIR ...	7	0.000			
1286 20190219_09	MIQI auto clean interphase		caton AUTO cleaning method interphase	Default	Cations_AUT ...	8	0.000			
1287 20190219_10	MIQI		caton AUTO cleaning method interphase	Default	Cations_AUT ...	9	0.000			

System Status: Ready

Not Scanning

4. Secondly, select the correct inlet file, double click on the line. Or one click and click on "OK".

The screenshot shows the Masslynx software interface with a sample list table. The table has columns for File Name, Sample ID, File Text, MS File, MS Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc A, and Quan Reference. A dialog box titled 'Inlet Methods' is open, showing a list of methods. The 'Cations_SIR 10min' method is highlighted in blue, and the 'OK' button is visible at the bottom of the dialog.

5. Copy the sample name given in the MS sample list and past into a line in the IC software (Ctrl + C and Ctrl + V). Note: pay attention to the correct IC method, correct position of the vial, correct sample name. IC-software: Double click on an empty row (screen pops up). Fill in the correct details.

The screenshot shows the IC software interface with a sample list table. A dialog box titled 'Edit line - Working sample table - Workplace Workplace' is open, showing fields for Method, Sample, Injections, Volume, Dilution, and Sample amount. The 'Cations - inorganic' method is selected. The 'OK' button is visible at the bottom of the dialog.

6. Always check if both instruments are well communicated and same number of total analysis.

- Click on "play". A Mass Lynx screen pops up, click on yes (it means that it's saving the sample list).

- Another screen pops up: Click on "OK". (It means that the software is asking to submit the selected rows to the queue and wait for a signal from the IC to start the analysis).

- After clicking "OK" at step 8, the first analysis of the selected rows will have a green color. Meaning it's waiting for a signal from the IC. Then click on "start" in the IC

The screenshot shows the 'Pyroprof_CationMethod_Carlos - Samples 1804 to 1804: Sample 1804 Acquiring' window. On the left, there are control panels for 'MS Status' (Ready), 'LC Status' (Ready), and 'System Status' (Ready). The main area is a table with columns: File Name, Sample ID, File Test, MS File, MS Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc A, and Quan Reference. The table lists 30 samples, with the first row (Sample 1804) highlighted in green. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'Acquiring ...' and 'Shutdown Disabled'.

The screenshot shows the 'Magic NH 3.1 - Workplace' interface. The top left has 'Run' and 'Determination series' buttons. Below is a 'Sample data' table with columns: Method, Ident, Sample type, Position, Injections, Status, Volume, and Dilution. The 'Live display 1 - 542 ppm-1: Cations - Robustness experiment G-1' window shows a chromatogram with a y-axis labeled 'µS/cm' and an x-axis labeled 'min'. The 'Watch window - Cations - isocratic' shows real-time parameters: Pump An Flow (0.0 µl/min), Pump An Pressure (12.9 MPa), Column thermostat Temperature (25.0 °C), Conductivity detector Conductivity (715.27 µS/cm), Tower Rack position (52), and Injector An Position. The 'Main program' window shows a list of events with columns: Time, Device, Module, Command, Parameter, and Comment.

10 Processing data

The next step after an analysis is done is processing data. With this software package it is possible to process data in multiple ways. Viewing chromatograms and spectra in MassLynx, chromatograms in the IC & studying all results in targetLynx. The way of processing data in each software is described in the separate chapters/paragraphs.

10.1 Processing data: View chromatogram in MassLynx

1. Select the row of the analysis you wish to view the results of. To select multiple rows, drag from top to bottom of the selected rows (Ctrl + click does not work).
2. Click on chromatogram (new window pops up, see step 3).

The screenshot displays the MassLynx software interface. The main window shows a table of analysis results. The columns are: Sample ID, File Text, MS File, MS Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc-A, and Quan Reference. The 'Chromatogram' button is highlighted in red. The 'System Status' is also highlighted in red. The interface includes a sidebar with 'MS Status' and 'LC Status' indicators, and a bottom status bar showing 'Ready' and 'Acquiring...'.

Sample ID	File Text	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Bottle	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc-A	Quan Reference
1758	20180313_01 1spn-18ca	22	Default	Default	12	0.000			
1759	20180313_02 MMQ	22	Default	Default	13	0.000			
1760	20180313_03 NYEE_1ed,917spn-2	22	Default	Default	14	0.000			
1761	20180313_04 NYEE_1ed,7465-3101	22	Default	Default	15	0.000			
1762	20180313_05 NYEE_1ed,73spn-1	22	Default	Default	16	0.000			
1763	20180313_06 NYEE_1ed,918-2	22	Default	Default	17	0.000			
1764	20180313_07 NYEE_1ed,917spn-1	22	Default	Default	18	0.000			
1765	20180313_08 ind 2ppm-1	22	Default	Default	19	0.000			
1766	20180313_09 MMQ-1	22	Default	Default	20	0.000			
1767	20180313_10 NYEE_1ed,23nb-1	22	Default	Default	21	0.000			
1768	20180313_11 NYEE_1ed,218-2	22	Default	Default	22	0.000			
1769	20180313_12 NYEE_1ed,217spn-1	22	Default	Default	23	0.000			
1770	20180313_13 NYEE_1ed,218-1	22	Default	Default	24	0.000			
1771	20180313_14 NYEE_1ed,78-1	22	Default	Default	25	0.000			
1772	20180313_15 ind 2ppm-2	22	Default	Default	26	0.000			
1773	20180313_16 MMQ-2	22	Default	Default	27	0.000			
1774	20180313_17 NYEE_1ed,9185-3101	22	Default	Default	28	0.000			
1775	20180313_18 NYEE_1ed,218-3	22	Default	Default	29	0.000			
1776	20180313_19 NYEE_1ed,918spn-1	22	Default	Default	30	0.000			
1777	20180313_20 NYEE_1ed,918spn-2	22	Default	Default	31	0.000			
1778	20180313_21 NYEE_1ed,918spn-2	22	Default	Default	32	0.000			
1779	20180313_22 ind 2ppm-3	22	Default	Default	33	0.000			
1780	20180313_23 MMQ-3	22	Default	Default	34	0.000			
1781	20180313_24 NYEE_1ed,918spn-2	22	Default	Default	35	0.000			
1782	20180313_25 NYEE_1ed,718-2	22	Default	Default	36	0.000			
1783	20180313_26 NYEE_1ed,917spn-2	22	Default	Default	37	0.000			
1784	20180313_27 NYEE_1ed,917spn-1	22	Default	Default	38	0.000			
1785	20180313_28 NYEE_1ed,918spn-1	22	Default	Default	39	0.000			
1786	20180313_29 ind 2ppm-4	22	Default	Default	40	0.000			
1787	20180313_30 MMQ-4	22	Default	Default	41	0.000			
1788	20180313_31 NYEE_1ed,918-1	22	Default	Default	42	0.000			
1789	20180313_32 NYEE_1ed,918spn-2	22	Default	Default	43	0.000			
1790	20180313_33 NYEE_1ed,918spn-2	22	Default	Default	44	0.000			
1791	20180313_34 NYEE_1ed,917spn-2	22	Default	Default	45	0.000			
1792	20180313_35 NYEE_1ed,918-3	22	Default	Default	46	0.000			
1793	20180313_36 ind 2ppm-5	22	Default	Default	47	0.000			
1794	20180313_37 MMQ-5	22	Default	Default	48	0.000			
1795	20180313_38 NYEE_1ed,918spn-1	22	Default	Default	49	0.000			
1796	20180313_39 NYEE_1ed,917spn-2	22	Default	Default	50	0.000			
1797	20180313_40 NYEE_1ed,218-3	22	Default	Default	51	0.000			
1798	20180313_41 NYEE_1ed,918-2	22	Default	Default	52	0.000			
1799	20180313_42 NYEE_1ed,918-1	22	Default	Default	53	0.000			
1800	20180313_43 NYEE_1ed,218spn-1	22	Default	Default	54	0.000			
1801	20180313_44 ind 2ppm-6	22	Default	Default	55	0.000			
1802	20180313_01 MMQ-1	22	Default	Default	1	0.000			
1803	20180313_02 ind 1ppm-1	22	Default	Default	2	0.000			
1804	20180313_03 ind 1ppm-10ca:Robustness experiment G-1	10	Default	Default	3	0.000			

- This new window is a chromatogram with several ions which are analysed. But not all! To view all ions go to step 4. (1 is the menu with all options with the chromatogram, 2 the date/ the file name of the analysis, 3 the name of the ion, 4 expand button to view the original chromatogram)

- Click on display-> TIC.

5. Select the ions (from manganese till lead) Ctrl + drag

6. The dummy channels is not necessary so you can skip that one by unselecting it. Ctrl + click on dummy. The click on "ok".

7. Optional is to follow an analysis live. This is only possible if the row of analysis that is going on is selected at step 1. After been through all the steps select the "clock icon" (see red circle on the picture below). Meaning a live display is shows of the current analysis. Note: when the instrument is going to the next analysis the chromatogram changes as well.

10.1.1 Viewing spectra

Double click on a peak in a chromatogram. A spectrum will pop up. In here you can see the height of the peaks

10.2 Processing data: TargetLynx

10.2.1 How to open an analysis in TargetLynx

1. Select a row you wish to view the analysis. It is possible to view multiple analysis at once. If that is the case then sort those analysis based on sample group. See chapter 9.2.2
2. Click on "shortcut", "TargetLynx", "Process samples" then "OK".

3. A new window pops up. This is TargetLynx. This software has multiple options which are very handy. 1: TargetLynx icon, 2: Open file & Save, 3: View previous sample & View next sample, 4: View previous ion & View next ion, 5: Display default (press the button when you accidentally zoom in while dragging the purple area of the peak), 6: Audit log (log which shows which chromatogram was adjusted), 7: Help

- a. If you click on the small arrow next to the View next sample button (nr 3). A list with file names of the selected analysis appears. If you click on one of those file names then the chromatogram jumps to that analysis.

- b. If you click on the small arrow next to the View next ion button (nr 4). A list with ions included in the method appears. If you click on one of those ions then the chromatogram jumps to that ion of the selected analysis.

10.2.2 How to sort on sample group

If the analysis of interest are not right after each other in order, it's still possible to sort them right after each other.

1. Type a letter from the alphabet in one of the categories "sample group". The letter Z is recommended because the software will sort them at the end of the list. Or you could chose a name for the group of samples.

The screenshot shows a software interface with a table of sample data. The table has columns for File Name, Sample ID, MS File, MS Tune File, Inlet File, Bottle, Inject Volume, Sample Type, Conc.A, Quan Reference, and Sample Group. A context menu is open over the 'Sample Group' column, showing options like 'Sort', 'Sample Group', and 'Acquisition File'. The 'Sample Group' column is highlighted, and the 'Sort' option is selected.

File Name	Sample ID	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Bottle	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc.A	Quan Reference	Sample Group
2002	20190401_34	20190320_32	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	41	0.000		
2003	20190401_35	20190320_33	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	42	0.000		
2004	20190401_36	20190320_34	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	43	0.000		
2005	20190401_37	20190320_35	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	44	0.000		
2006	20190401_38	20190320_36	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	45	0.000		
2007	20190401_39	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	46	0.000		
2008	20190401_40	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	47	0.000		
2009	20190401_41	20190320_43	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	48	0.000		
2000	20190401_42	20190320_44	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	49	0.000		
2001	20190401_43	20190320_47	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	52	0.000		
2002	20190401_44	20190320_48	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	53	0.000		
2003	20190401_45	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	54	0.000		
2004	20190401_46	M&M	catons AUTO clearing method interphase	Default	Catons_AUTO clearing method for interp.	55	0.000			
2005	20190402_01	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	1	0.000		
2006	20190402_02	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	2	0.000		
2007	20190402_03	std 1ppm-18cat,2	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	3	0.000		
2008	20190402_04	Si 0x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	4	0.000		
2009	20190402_05	Si 1x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	5	0.000		
2040	20190402_06	Si 2x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	6	0.000		
2041	20190402_07	Si 5x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	7	0.000		
2042	20190402_08	Si 10x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	8	0.000		
2043	20190402_09	Si 20x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	9	0.000		
2044	20190402_10	Si 50x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	10	0.000		
2045	20190402_11	Si 100x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	11	0.000		
2046	20190402_12	Si 200x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	12	0.000		
2047	20190402_13	Si 500x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	13	0.000		
2048	20190402_14	Si 1000x LOD	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	14	0.000		
2049	20190402_15	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	15	0.000		
2050	20190402_16	20190320_49	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	16	0.000		
2051	20190402_17	20190320_50	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	17	0.000		
2052	20190402_18	20190320_51	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	18	0.000		
2053	20190402_19	20190320_52	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	19	0.000		
2054	20190402_20	20190320_53	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	20	0.000		
2055	20190402_21	20190320_54	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	21	0.000		
2056	20190402_22	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	22	0.000		2
2057	20190402_23	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	23	0.000		
2058	20190402_24	20190320_61	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	24	0.000		
2059	20190402_25	20190320_62	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	25	0.000		
2060	20190402_26	20190320_63	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	26	0.000		
2061	20190402_27	20190320_64	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	27	0.000		
2062	20190402_28	20190320_65	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	28	0.000		
2063	20190402_29	20190320_66	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	29	0.000		
2064	20190402_30	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	30	0.000		2
2065	20190402_31	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	31	0.000		
2066	20190402_32	20190320_73	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	32	0.000		
2067	20190402_33	20190320_74	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	33	0.000		
2068	20190402_34	20190320_75	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	34	0.000		
2069	20190402_35	20190320_76	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	35	0.000		
2070	20190402_36	20190320_77	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	36	0.000		
2071	20190402_37	20190320_78	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	37	0.000		
2072	20190402_38	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	38	0.000		2
2073	20190402_39	M&M	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	39	0.000		
2074	20190402_40	20190320_85	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	40	0.000		
2075	20190402_41	20190320_86	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	41	0.000		
2076	20190402_42	20190320_87	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	42	0.000		
2077	20190402_43	20190320_88	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	43	0.000		
2078	20190402_44	20190320_89	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	44	0.000		
2079	20190402_45	20190320_90	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	45	0.000		
2080	20190402_46	std 1ppm-18cat	22	Catons SIR	Default	Catons_SIR_23min	46	0.000		
2081	20190402_47	M&M	catons AUTO clearing method interphase	Default	Catons_AUTO clearing method for interp.	47	0.000			

- 2. After typing the letter in all those rows you wish. Click on "sample", "sort" and then on "sample group". See figure below that the list sorted based on sample group.

File Name	Sample ID	File Test	MS File	MS Tune File	Inlet File	Bottle	Inject Volume	Sample Type	Conc.A	Quan Reference	Sample Group
20190402_34	20190328_75	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	34	0.000				
2023	20190402_35	20190328_76	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	35	0.000			
2024	20190402_36	20190328_77	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	36	0.000			
2025	20190402_37	20190328_78	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	37	0.000			
2026	20190402_38	INAG	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	38	0.000			
2027	20190402_40	20190328_85	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	40	0.000			
2028	20190402_41	20190328_86	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	41	0.000			
2029	20190402_42	20190328_87	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	42	0.000			
2030	20190402_43	20190328_88	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	43	0.000			
2031	20190402_44	20190328_89	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	44	0.000			
2032	20190402_45	20190328_90	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	45	0.000			
2033	20190402_46	in4 1pm-18ca	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	46	0.000			
2034	20190402_47	INAG	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	47	0.000			
2035	20190322_02	in4 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_15min	32	0.000			Robustness
2036	20190328_06	Robustness exp A - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 15min		Default	Caton_SIR_15min	6	0.000			Robustness A
2037	20190328_07	Robustness exp A-1 - 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 15min		Default	Caton_SIR_15min	6	0.000			Robustness A
2038	20190328_08	Robustness exp A-1 - 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 15min		Default	Caton_SIR_15min	7	0.000			Robustness A
2039	20190321_01	Robustness exp A - repeat 1pm-18ca-1exp1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_AUTO cleaning method for intep.	18	0.000			Robustness A
2040	20190321_02	Robustness exp A - repeat 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_AUTO cleaning method for intep.	19	0.000			Robustness A
2041	20190321_03	Robustness exp A - repeat 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_AUTO cleaning method for intep.	20	0.000			Robustness A
2042	20190320_03	Robustness exp B - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	11	0.000			Robustness B
2043	20190320_06	Robustness exp B - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	14	0.000			Robustness B
2044	20190320_07	Robustness exp B - 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	15	0.000			Robustness B
2045	20190320_08	Robustness exp B - 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	16	0.000			Robustness B
2046	20190321_07	Robustness exp D - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	24	0.000			Robustness D
2047	20190321_08	Robustness exp D - 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	25	0.000			Robustness D
2048	20190321_09	Robustness exp D - 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	26	0.000			Robustness D
2049	20190322_02	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	29	0.000			Robustness E
2050	20190322_03	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	30	0.000			Robustness E
2051	20190322_04	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	31	0.000			Robustness E
2052	20190322_05	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-4	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	32	0.000			Robustness E
2053	20190322_06	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-5	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	33	0.000			Robustness E
2054	20190322_07	Robustness exp E - 1pm-18ca-6	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	34	0.000			Robustness E
2055	20190322_08	Robustness exp F - 1pm-18ca-1	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	2	0.000			Robustness F
2056	20190322_09	Robustness exp F - 1pm-18ca-2	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	3	0.000			Robustness F
2057	20190322_10	Robustness exp F - 1pm-18ca-3	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	4	0.000			Robustness F
2058	20190322_11	Robustness exp F - 1pm-18ca-4	16 Caton SIR 45min Robustness exp B		Default	Caton_SIR 45min Robustness expB	5	0.000			Robustness F
2059	20190319_03	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment G-1	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	3	0.000			Robustness G
2060	20190319_04	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment G-2	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	4	0.000			Robustness G
2061	20190319_05	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment G-3	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	5	0.000			Robustness G
2062	20190319_06	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment G-4	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	6	0.000			Robustness G
2063	20190319_08	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment H-1	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	8	0.000			Robustness H
2064	20190319_09	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment H-2	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	9	0.000			Robustness H
2065	20190319_10	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment H-3	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp G		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness expG	10	0.000			Robustness H
2066	20190321_02	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp-1	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	26	0.000			Robustness J
2067	20190321_03	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp-2	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	27	0.000			Robustness J
2068	20190321_04	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp-3	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	28	0.000			Robustness J
2069	20190321_05	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp-4	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	29	0.000			Robustness J
2070	20190321_06	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-1	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	14	0.000			Robustness L
2071	20190320_05	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-2	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	15	0.000			Robustness L
2072	20190320_06	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-1 test-1	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	16	0.000			Robustness L
2073	20190320_08	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-1 test-2	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	18	0.000			Robustness L
2074	20190320_09	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-1 test-3	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	19	0.000			Robustness L
2075	20190320_10	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness expment L-1 test-4	18 Caton SIR 33min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 33min Robustness exp L	20	0.000			Robustness L
2076	20190320_11	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp L-1	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	21	0.000			Robustness L
2077	20190320_12	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp L-2	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	22	0.000			Robustness L
2078	20190320_13	S14 1pm-18ca-10catons-Robustness exp L-3	18 Caton SIR 40min Robustness exp L		Default	Caton_SIR 40min Robustness exp L	23	0.000			Robustness L
2079	20190402_29	in4 1pm-18ca	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	32	0.000			z
2080	20190402_30	in4 1pm-18ca	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	30	0.000			z
2081	20190402_38	in4 1pm-18ca	22 Caton SIR		Default	Caton_SIR_23min	38	0.000			z

10.2.3 How to export the TargetLynx data into an Excel file.

1. Click on "Edit", "Copy", "Complete summary**"
2. Open an excel file on the IC-MS computer
3. Paste.
4. Then it is possible to copy the Excel file into your own computer by taking over the control from your own desk.

*The complete summary allows to copy all data from all the selected analysis and all ions.
 The current summary only copies the data from the ion you are viewing.

The screenshot displays the TargetLynx software interface. At the top, there's a menu bar with options like File, Edit, View, Display, Processing, Window, and Help. Below the menu is a toolbar with various icons. The main window is divided into several sections:

- Top Panel:** Shows 'Method: ...' and 'Current Summary' with a 'Complete Summary' button.
- Table:** A large table with columns for 'Peak No.', 'Peak Name', 'Area', 'Height', 'Width', 'Retention Time', 'Abundance', 'Signal', 'Quantity', 'Purity', and 'ID'. It lists various peaks with their corresponding data.
- Chromatogram:** A plot showing signal intensity versus retention time. Several peaks are labeled with their retention times (e.g., 2.81, 2.98, 3.10, 3.30, 3.46, 3.60).
- Bottom Panel:** A 'System Status' section with a 'Ready' indicator and a 'System Status' button.

10.2.4 How to adjust the layout in TargetLynx

1. Right click on the column
2. Click on "Change column order" (screen pops up)

3. Select the columns you wish to add in the "Available Columns", click on "add" or "remove". After the layout is as choice then click on "ok". Save this Layout under a name.

10.3 Processing data: IC

See " Ionchromatograaf Applikon juni 2016"

The screenshot displays the MagIC software interface for data processing. The main window is titled 'MagIC New 3.1 - MagIC Net'. It features a menu bar (File, Edit, View, Determinations, Tools, Help) and a toolbar. The central area is divided into several panels:

- Determination overview:** A table listing various determinations with columns for Determination start, Ident, Sample type, Method name, User (short name), Info 1, and Modification comment. The table shows multiple entries for different samples and methods, including 'PMNQ' and 'SR 100 X LOD'.
- Curves 1 - std 1 ppm-18cat:** A chromatogram plot showing detector response over time (0.5 to 9.0 minutes). Several peaks are labeled with their retention times: 1.30, 2.27, 3.87, 4.87, 6.07, 6.98, 8.41, and 12.20. The y-axis is labeled 'µS/cm' and ranges from 655.80 to 656.80.
- Information:** A panel providing details about the analysis, including:
 - Data source: Conductivity detector 1 (850 Professional IC 1)
 - Channel: Conductivity
 - Mode: 25.0 min
 - Recording time: 25.0 min
 - Integration: Automatically
 - Column type: Metrosep C Supp 1 - 250/4.0
 - Eluent composition: not defined
 - Flow: 1.000 mL/min
 - Maximum flow monitored: Yes
 - Pressure: 14.83 MPa
 - Maximum pressure monitored: Yes
 - Temperature: 30.0 °C
- Results:** A table showing the results for 'Cations'. The table has columns for Component name, Retention time [min], Height [µS/cm], Area [µS/cm x min], and Concentration [ppm].

Component name	Retention time [min]	Height [µS/cm]	Area [µS/cm x min]	Concentration [ppm]
Lithium	6.07	0.347	0.062	invalid
Sodium	8.41	0.132	0.045	invalid
Ammonium	9.68	0.142	0.058	invalid
Potassium	12.20	0.020	0.004	invalid

11 Opening the calibration file

1. Go to the MS Tune page
2. Click on "Calibration"
3. Click on "set Linked calibration".

4. A screen pops up. This is the MS calibration file. If it is not the correct file then open the correct file.

12 Adjust the noise range

Every ion has a noise range but sometimes due to difference in separation the noise range should be adjusted. For this a chromatogram of a good separation is necessary.

1. Open a chromatogram of a good separation
2. Open Edit Method
3. Click on "Update", "Noise range"
4. Go to the ion of interest in edit method
5. Go to the chromatogram and to the specific ion selected.
6. Drag with the right click of the mouse over the noise range of the peak. Noise range is the point where the peak start but still can be considered as noise till the point of the peak where actually the peak looks like a peak.

The screenshot displays the TargetLynx Method Editor interface. On the left, a vertical stack of chromatograms shows Total Ion Chromatograms (TIC) for various ions. The top chromatogram is for Calcium (16: SIR of 3 Channels ES+), with peaks labeled at 6.67, 7.23, 7.38, 7.86, and 8.38. The right panel shows the 'Update' menu with 'Noise Range' selected. Below the menu, the 'Compound' list includes Calcium (16), which is highlighted. The 'Signal To Noise Parameters' section is expanded, showing settings for Calcium, such as 'Propagate Signal To Noise Parameters?' (checked), 'Signal-to-noise method' (Peak-to-Peak), and 'Flag Minimum Signal/Noise Ratio' (3.00).

Compound	Value
1: Urea	
2: Ammonia	
3: Sodium	
4: Magnesium	
5: Potassium	
6: Strontium	
7: Ethylammonium	
8: Iron II high	
9: Nickel	
10: Cobalt	
11: Aluminum	
12: Copper	
13: Lithium	
14: Dicyandiamide	
15: Barium	
16: Calcium	
17: Manganese	
18: Iron II	
19: Dummy Channel	
20: Cadmium	
21: Zinc	
22: Cesium	
23: Gadolinium	
24: Lead	

Parameter	Value
Propagate Calibration Settings?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Minimum Coefficient of Determination	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0.500000
Propagate Signal To Noise Parameters?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Signal-to-noise method	Peak-to-Peak
Noise window start (min)	6.0300
Noise window end (min)	6.7600
Measure peak signal level from	Peak Baseline
Detection Limit Factor	0.0000
Quantitation Limit Factor	0.0000
Flag Minimum Signal/Noise Ratio	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3.00
Propagate Retention Time Parameters?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Predicted RT (mins)	7.2500
Flag RT Tolerance?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Lower Retention Time Tolerance (%)	0.00
Upper Retention Time Tolerance (%)	0.00
Update Method Times Using Multiple Samples?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Maximum Concentration Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0.0000
Reporting Concentration Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0.0000
Always Print?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES
Propagate Peak Asymmetry Criteria?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Measure at Height (%)	0.00
Expected Asymmetry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0.0000
Asymmetry Window (%)	0.00
Generate Expected Asymmetry from Reference P...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO

13 Troubleshooting

See maintenance map “Manual IC-MS map”.

There is a blue coloured map behind the IC-MS autosampler. This map contains a printed manual of the Waters MS. There were some problems to which the manuals did not give a solution. These problems were discussed via email with Marijn van Hulle, contact person from Waters. These emails are printed and can be found in the “Manual IC-MS map”.

Difference in total analysis in both IC and MS

It is possible that the IC is 1 analysis short, but it is also possible that the MS is 1 analysis short in the list.

Situation when the MS is 1 analysis short:

The following day after a night sequence you notice that the total number of analysis in both software's don't match. There are 20 analysis. So 20 rows in the IC sample table but there are 19 rows in the MS list. If the total runs are not the same then in the MS list the results don't match to the names. Adjust the names given in the MS list. Why adjust the MS list? Because the IC injects the sample and also analyses the sample. The MS depends on the IC.

Problems which can occur when the IC is 1 analysis short:

If the IC is 1 analysis short then that means that the MS has 1 row left, which means that the MS will not automatically shut down (if this option was selected) after the last analysis. Because the MS has still 1 row in the queue and is waiting for contact with the IC.

Meaning:

- Still an analysis in the queue
- The MS tune method *default.ipr* is still loaded.
- The desolvation gas is still on 1200L/Hr
- MS still on
- Valve in LC position
- Red light in Inlet Method
- Red light in System status
- The UPLC software is still pumping with cleaning eluent

Solution: Delete the pending analysis in the queue. Stop the pumping in the UPLC software, if it is pumping see paragraph “ ”. Reset the communications in the Inlet method software see chapter “ ”.

Chromatogram with bad peak shapes.

Air bubbles in either the tubing from the eluent bottle or air bubbles in the tubing from the injector tower.

Accidentally adjusting the shutdown method

It can happen that in a hurry the shutdown method is modified by mistake. For example the desolvation gas is on 400L/Hr but by mistake it is changed to 1200L/Hr. This means that after the whole sequence the instrument will still have a desolvation gas of 1200 Litters per Hour. That's why there are 2 methods in the MS Tune we are working with (Default and shutdown). When starting the day always look at top left in which method the MS Tune is configured in. If the shutdown method is loaded just open the default file.

Forgetting to checkmark the shutdown after last analysis in the IC-software.

Worst case scenario is to forget to checkmark the auto shutdown in the IC. If a long sequence is launched and will run for the weekend and that option was not check marked then the IC will keep on pumping the eluent through the system. At some point there won't be any eluent leftover to pump so instead it will pump air through the whole system which is not the best thing.

Not selecting the right method

It can happen that for some reason the wrong method is selected. Because for one analysis you need to select three methods it can go wrong.

Situation 1: Selected the AUTO cleaning method while in the MS the analysing method is selected.

The IC will have different parameters and will run longer than the MS. The MS will record a chromatogram but it won't be any use due to the different parameters the separation will be different.

Situation 2: Selected the analysing method in the IC while in auto cleaning method is selected in the MS.

The IC will run shorter than the MS. Due the wrong method combination it's possible that the MS interphase will not be clean automatically.

Situation 3: Wrong combination of methods in the MS

If in the MS there is a wrong combination of the Inlet file and MS file then the MS will give an error and you cannot start the analysis. See below table with possible combinations. *Note: name of the methods are without prejudice.*

MS file	Inlet File
22 Cation SIR	Cations_SIR 23min
22 cations SIR+MS	Cations_SIR 23min
Cations AUTO cleaning method interphase	Cations_AUTO cleaning method for interphase

If eluent is not well prepared

Not well prepared eluent can have effect on the separation of the ions. If there is a huge difference then it is possible that the retention time has shifted outside of the retention time window.

Error MS full scan method

After the calibration the MS Full scan method cannot be worked with because it gives an error. There is no solution for it. The contact person has already informed and is looking for an solution.

Auto stop when pressure of the IC fails

The IC automatically stop equilibrating or analysing when the pressure is too high. The maximum pressure is 15 MPa. When this happens equilibrate again starting from 0.8ml/min.

14 Overview of the options in the MassLynx software

15 Overview of the options in IC software

